

DESIGN AND OPTIMIZATION OF GRADIENT CELLULAR STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Cellular honeycombs have been widely used for a variety of engineering applications, from advanced aircraft design, to modern wind turbines where there is need for lightweight structures with high stiffness and strength. Functionally graded cellular structures are characterized by a gradual variation of cell size, shape and wall thickness over a prescribed volume. The gradient topology leads to a continuous distribution of curvatures, stiffness and energy absorption capability. In this work we present a numerical methodology for design of gradient auxetic cellular structures with a wide range of different negative Poisson's ratios. The proposed methodology is based on a combination of finite element method and a genetic algorithm. The problem is formulated as an optimization problem of finding cell size, shape and wall thickness of cellular structures with prescribed behavioral requirements. Different cellular structures are generated and evolved using the genetic algorithm and the behavior of each cellular structure is analyzed using the finite element method to evaluate its fitness in competition with other generated structures. Numerical examples show that it is possible to design a large number of new auxetic materials, each with a different value of negative Poisson's ratio. The proposed methodology can be used as an effective method to tailor new materials with prescribed values of negative (or positive) Poisson's ratio. The methodology can also be used to optimize other material properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cellular honeycombs have been widely used for a variety of engineering applications, from advanced aircraft design, to modern wind turbines where there is need for lightweight structures with high stiffness and strength [1]. Functionally graded cellular structures are characterized by a gradual variation of cell size, shape and wall thickness over a prescribed volume. The gradient topology leads to a continuous distribution of curvatures, stiffness and energy absorption capability. Lim [2] proposed a gradient cellular structure made of center symmetric regular cells by varying the internal cell angle row by row. The gradient cellular core provided the design of a functionally graded beam with Poisson-curving characteristics. Lira and Scarpa [3] provided a feasible solution to optimize the transverse shear stiffness of the honeycomb through changing the horizontal rib thickness across the whole panel. The use of a step-wise honeycomb core was introduced by Lira et al. [4] as a filler for aeroengine fan blades, showing a significant decrease in terms of mass and mass modal displacement compared to existing baseline fan blade configurations. Ajdari et al. [5] introduced a density gradient cellular structure by a gradual change of the cell wall thickness, and investigated its deformation mechanism under low and high crushing velocities. The decrease of the honeycomb relative density along the crushing direction significantly enhanced the energy absorption at early stage. Hou et al. [6] described the bending and failure behavior of polymorphic honeycomb topologies consisting of gradient variations of the horizontal rib length and cell internal across the surface of the cellular structures. It was found that the aspect ratio and the extent of gradient (i.e. the horizontal rib length growth rate or the internal angle increment) have a significant influence on the flexural properties of the sandwich panels with angle gradient cores.

In this work we present a numerical methodology for design of gradient auxetic cellular structures with a wide range of different negative Poisson's ratios. The proposed methodology is based on a combination of finite element method and a genetic algorithm. The problem is formulated as an optimization problem of finding cell size, shape and wall thickness of cellular structures with prescribed behavioral requirements. Different cellular structures are generated and evolved using the genetic algorithm and the behavior of each cellular structure is analyzed using the finite element method to evaluate its fitness in competition with other generated structures. Numerical examples show that it is possible to design a large number of new auxetic materials, each with a different value of negative Poisson's ratio. The proposed methodology can be used as an effective method to tailor new materials with prescribed values of negative (or positive) Poisson's ratio. The methodology can also be used to optimize other material properties.

2 GRADIENT CELLULAR STRUCTURE

In this work we examine the gradient cellular structure topology based on a center symmetric unit cell, with varying cell wall thickness and internal cell angle, as shown in Figure 1. The geometry of the cellular structure is defined by the internal cell angle θ , cell wall thickness t , horizontal ribs length H and oblique ribs length L , as shown in Figure 2.

(a) Thickness graded cellular structure (b) Angle graded cellular structures

Figure 1: Gradient cellular structure.

Figure 2: geometry of the cellular structure cell.

3 METHODOLOGY

The developed methodology is based on a combination of the Finite Element Method (FEM) and Genetic Algorithm (GA). The problem is formulated as an optimization problem of finding ribs thickness and internal angle distribution with prescribed behavioral requirements.

Different distribution of ribs thickness and internal angles are generated and evolved using the principles of GA and the behavior of each structure is analyzed using the Finite Element Method to evaluate its fitness in competition with other generated structures. During successive generations the GA operators gradually improve the fitness of the solution and direct the search towards the optimal or near optimal solution.

3.1 Genetic Algorithm

Genetic Algorithm has received much attention regarding their potential as global optimization techniques for problems with large and complex search spaces. GA has many advantages over the traditional optimization methods. In particular, they do not require function derivatives and work on function evaluations alone. They have a better possibility of locating the global optimum because they search a population of points rather than a single point and they can allow for consideration of design spaces consisting of a mix of continuous and discrete variables. GA operates on a population of trial solutions that are initially generated at random. The GA seeks to maximize the fitness of the population by selecting the fittest individuals, based on Darwin's theory of survival of the fittest, and using their genetic information in mating and mutation operations to create a new population of solutions.

3.2 Finite Element model

A four-node shell was used to build the finite element model of the gradient cellular structure in this work. A linear elastic analysis is employed to analyze the behavior of the structures under a prescribed displacement. The microstructures generated by the GA are analyzed using the FE method to evaluate the fitness of each structure in competition with other structures in the population. The output of the FE analysis is fitness function (weight), displacement and stress for each structure which is returned as the objective function to be optimized by the GA.

3.3 Optimization of gradient cellular structure

In general an optimization problem involves minimization (or maximization) of an objective function subject to a set of constraints and can be formulated as:

$$\text{Find } x \in R_k \text{ to}$$

$$\text{Minimize } f(x)$$

$$\text{Subject to } g_i(x) \leq 0 \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

$$x_j^L \leq x_j \leq x_j^U \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, k$$

where, x is vector of design variables, $f(x)$ is objective function, $g(x)$ represents the constraint functions, x_j^L and x_j^U are the lower and upper bounds of the design variables.

In this study, geometry (shape) and size optimization methods are used to obtain microstructures for cellular structures. For the geometry optimization method the variables are considered as the X and Y coordinates in 2D (and X, Y and Z coordinates in 3D) while in the size optimization approach the internal cell angle are the variables.

The methodology is based on a combination of a GA and the FE method. Initially a population of solutions is generated randomly using the GA. The design variables in each solution are used to construct FE model of the structure. A prescribed displacement is applied to the structures in the vertical direction and the FE method is used to calculate the average displacement(s) in the lateral direction(s) and the value(s) of Poisson's ratio(s) of the structure which are returned to the GA to be minimized. The GA uses three main genetic operators to generate a new population of solutions for next generation. The procedure continues until the termination criterion is satisfied. Figure 3 shows the flowchart of the proposed optimization process.

Figure 3: Flowchart of the procedure adopted in the proposed methodology.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section a number of examples are presented in order to verify the methodology. It will be shown that using the proposed method it is possible to obtain a large number of microstructures with different values of geometry parameters of the gradient cellular structure.

4.1 Thickness gradient cellular structures under torsion

In this example cell wall thickness t , the internal cell angle θ , oblique ribs length L , the ratio of horizontal ribs length and oblique ribs length H/L and the thickness gradient parameter β are considered as design variables and the objective is to minimize the weight of the structures. A 4×6 regular initial structure as shown in Figure 4 is used to verify the methodology. Two cases are considered. In the first case the torsion loads were applied in X direction while in the second case they were applied in Y direction during the optimization process.

Figure 5 shows the variation of the weight of the structures with the number of generations. It is shown that weight of the structures was decreased significantly as the number of generations was increased, especially at the early generations of the evolutionary process. For the first case, after 16 generations the minimum achieved weight was 0.08833 while for the second case, after 35 generations the minimum achieved weight was 0.054.

(a) Torsion in X direction (b) Torsion in Y direction

Figure 4: Boundary condition of rectangle gradient cellular structures.

(a) Torsion loads applied in X direction (b) Torsion loads applied in Y direction

Figure 5: Number of generations versus weight of gradient cellular structure.

4.2 Internal angle gradient cellular structures under torsion

Figure 6 shows the variation of the weight of the structures with the number of generations. It is shown that weight of the structures was decreased significantly as the number of generations was increased, especially at the early generations of the evolutionary process. For the first case, after 16 generations the minimum achieved weight was 0.08833 while for the second case, after 35 generations the minimum achieved weight was 0.054.

(a) Torsion loads applied in X direction (b) Torsion loads applied in Y direction

Figure 6: Number of generations versus weight of gradient cellular structure.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A numerical methodology for design of gradient auxetic cellular structures based on a combination of finite element method and a genetic algorithm was proposed.

The problem is formulated as an optimization problem of finding cell size, shape and wall thickness of cellular structures with prescribed behavioral requirements. Different cellular structures are generated and evolved using the genetic algorithm and the behavior of each cellular structure is analyzed using the finite element method to evaluate its fitness in competition with other generated structures. Numerical examples show that it is possible to design a large number of new auxetic materials, each with a different value of negative Poisson's ratio. The proposed methodology can be used as an effective method to tailor new materials with prescribed values of negative (or positive)

Poisson's ratio. The methodology can also be used to optimize other material properties.

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